

INSTITUTIONALIZED MARGINALIZATION: EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF PARENTAL AND INSTITUTIONAL PRESSURES ON CAREER ASPIRATIONS AMONG DISADVANTAGED YOUTH IN PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

This research paper analyzes the parental pressure and institutional influence in determining students' careers or fields, referred to as "Imposed goals" in the private schools of District Tank and Dera Ismail Khan, Pakistan. It points out the problem of institutions being the source of providing Banking concept of education in the classrooms. The way institutions work and mold the students' goals according to their interests, gives rise to an education system focused solely on money rather than genuine learning in classrooms. The way parents psychologically develop children by urging them to become a doctor or an engineer from the very beginning of their schooling. Additionally, students are treated as commodities by institutions and teachers who compel them by suggesting to join affiliated colleges and specific academies for specific test preparation. This paper is an attempt to analyze the role of parents and institutions in formulating the goals of students.

Keywords: *imposed goals, institutional influence parental pressure.*

INTRODUCTION

Education is the weapon of empowerment in this modern society. The modern world has transformed from the battle ground of the past. Today, modern and civilized societies compete in the field of education. It is the key to explore the hidden truths of nature. Human beings are trying to have a complete control over universe. This is all because of knowledge, enlightenment and education. Education was the first and foremost preference of the founder of Pakistan, Quaid-e-Azam Muhammad Ali Jinnah. He repeatedly emphasized its importance to the youth of newly-formed nation. During his address to the student of the University of Karachi, he emphasized the importance of education by saying, "You are the

nation-builders of tomorrow and you must fully equip yourself by discipline, education and training for the arduous task lying ahead of you". Similarly, the nascent government of Pakistan, after receiving significant criticism, initiated compulsory education for children in 1959, following the footsteps of its founder. Similarly, recent changes to Article 25-A in 2010 states that "The State shall provide free and compulsory education to all children of the age of five to sixteen years in such manner as may be determined by law." However, Pakistani society consists of patriarchal families, where all decisions are made by the male members. Male members decide whether girls are allowed to pursue studies. Similarly, they impose their

unachieved goals on their children, demanding that they choose a specific field from the early childhood. Education is the beacon of light in the darkness of ignorance but in Pakistan and especially in the south-west districts like Tank and Dera Ismail Khan, it has become the source of dream fulfillment of parents. Pakistani children depend on other to make decisions for them, most of the youth choose their career following the tradition of family (Arif, Iqbal & Khalil 2019). Parents play a very critical role in shaping students' choice of career (Chen & Fouad, 2013; Fouad, Kim, Ghosh, Chang & Figueiredo, 2016). They limit their children' choice by creating around them a web of specific goals to hunt in the long run. These specific imposed goals are mostly related to medical and engineering fields. Students, at a very early age, internalize and assume those imposed goals. They try to give practical shape to those imposed goals by taking admission to various schools and colleges. However, these institutions take the form of Banking concept of education through Institutional policies. These institutions exploit students by promising admission to their affiliated best colleges and academies for specific entry test preparation like ETEA and MDCAT. These institutions play their part in modifying the goals of innocent students by keeping them to a certain track. Students blinded by the imposed goal believe in them and take admission. Throughout the educational journey they keep students to a specific track. They do not want student to distract from the imposed goal because they will be unable to sell or commodify students to the next affiliated college and then to academy. Similarly, these institutions use various methods to attract students. One and the foremost method they adopt by giving admission to very talented students who can easily pass the different medical and engineering entry test. They use these students for advertising and to shape the goals of average students. Students who are unable to score high marks in medical and engineering tests face various issues, often resulting in psychological distress. They are overwhelmed by a variety of thoughts even suicidal thoughts because they are unable to hunt their imposed dream.

Methodology

This research was carried out with 14-18 years old children from class 12 and onward, comprising a total of 65 students, 30 girls and 35 boys. Thirty out of sixty-five were from District Dera Ismail Khan and they were from the poor marginalized family background. However, the rest of thirty-five were from District Tank, who lived in Gara Ranwal and Gara Baloch. All students spoke Urdu fluently. Interviews and questionnaires the preferred forms of data collection were conducted in Urdu and then translated into English. All interviews were conducted in confidential manner with careful consideration given to the security and privacy of the students. All interviews were conducted in different locations to ensure the students' safety. Similarly, permission was obtained from the students' parents, and assent was sought from students themselves. Mostly students were from different schools, however, in District Dera Ismail Khan the students of Qurtuba public school and college were in majority. Moreover, in District Tank, the majority of students were from Iqra School and College. Through these interviews, the researcher was able to talk about the issue of Imposed goals students face. All interviews were recorded and questionnaire were printed and completed and translated into English and were analyzed according to the Banking a concept of education in Paulo Freire's book 'Pedagogy of the Oppressed' and Erikson's psychosocial development theory, specifically the stage of 'Identity vs. Role Confusion'. Similarly, the nature of much of the data was ordinal, and non-linear relationships between variables were expected; hence, the Spearman correlation analysis was conducted. This statistical test was especially fit for the identification of trends rather than any testing of causality, as many of the relationships in the data, such as those between family pressures and career dissatisfaction, are complex and multifactorial in nature.

Variables Measured:

Data collected within the questionnaire on three broad categories;

- **Demographic Variables:** Sex, level of education, and family income.

- **Parental Influence:** Items include family opinions about career, pressure exerted by parents, disregard for these career opinions, financial expectations and perceived autonomy in choice.
- **Institutional Influence:** School Expectations, Promotion of Affiliated Colleges, Subtle Encouragement toward Particular Fields, Financial Benefits, and Teacher Practices.
- **Psychological and Career Impact:** The statements covered the things in congruence with personal interests, regret fullness, intention to change career, pressures from peers, and perceptions of financial stability. All the variables used Likert scales ranging from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree, binary responses of Yes/No, and nominal categories to provide complete data for analysis.

Paulo Freire in his *Pedagogy of the Oppressed* says that education a ‘misguided’ system and ‘education is suffering from narration sickness’ (p.99). In the *Banking* a concept of education Paulo Freire says that this system of education tries to control thinking by reducing the creativity and critical thinking of the students and make them a passive learner or object. Banking concept of education considers the students as empty vessels to be filled with knowledge, like a coin bank. The task of the teacher is to ‘fill’ the students. Similarly, the consequences of this system are that they impose their goals on the students by limiting their creative thinking. These Institutions mold students’ thinking and they conform to the specific field shown by the institution such as medical and engineering. “The more students work at storing the deposits entrusted to them, the less they develop the critical consciousness which would result from their intervention in the world as transformers of that world. The more completely they accept the passive role imposed on them, the more they tend simply to adapt to the world as it is and to the fragmented view of reality deposited in them (p.73)”. So, in this system “the teacher chooses and enforces his choice, and the students comply (p.73)”. Moreover, “teacher confuses the authority of knowledge with his or her own professional authority, which she and he sets in opposition to the freedom of the students; (p.73)”. Students are marginalized through this learning because teacher stays at the center being the source

of everything and “the teacher knows everything and the students know nothing”. So, through the student’s ignorance they take advantage and exploit them by running their business which at the end cause severe consequences for poor students. Additionally, Erik Erikson’s psychosocial development theory, specifically the stage of ‘Identity vs. Role Confusion explains that how people grow and change throughout their lives by facing different problems. This theory explains that teenagers in their stage of identity vs Role confusion, figure out who they are and what they want to do. They develop a strong sense of identity if they are allowed to explore freely. But if other forces like parents or institutions force their decisions like choosing a career then teenagers feel confuse about their role which lead to regret and dissatisfaction later. “The young person, in search of a future role or occupational identity, may be overburdened by the expectations from parents or significant others” (Erikson, 1968, p. 120).

Similarly, different research highlights various factors that influence the long-term goals of individuals however family is among one of them and especially parents (Wahl & Blackhurst, 2000). Moreover, in the psychosocial development and the adjustment of children, parents play a significant role and especially in their career development (Lamborn, Mounts, Steinberg, & Dornbusch, 1991; Noller, 1994). Parental attachment, in many of family variables that influence the children’s goals, are embedded in long term processes (Ketterson & Blustein, 1997). However, dysfunctional family full of conflicts, negatively associate with the goals and vocational identity development of children (Hargrove, Creagh, & Burgess, 2002; Johnson et al., 1999; Ryan et al., 1996). According to (Schultheiss et al., 2001) some of the testifiers pointed out that their parents control their goals too much. However, young aspirants are more likely in exploring different goals when they are free to choose their own profession instead of parental obligations and expecting for a specific career or goal (Crockett & Bingham, 2000; Larson, 1995).

Literature Review

The purpose of this chapter is to review and organize literature related to the specific topic of

imposed goals on children and the role of parents and institutions. This has been discussed by various researchers. It has been discussed from the prospective of different communities, highlighting the issue of parental and institutional influence on the lives of children.

Arif, Iqbal, and Khalil (2019)) examined the factors that influence student's choices of academic careers in Pakistan. Similarly, their study investigates the career choices of students during secondary schooling and the problem they face in matching their career choices with their interests and academic performance while accommodating the parental wishes at the same time. Their study highlights the factors that play a significant role in the academic careers of students who are currently pursuing their study in university. The following seven factors: Family, Social, Economic, Self-efficacy, academic support, satisfaction and Dissatisfaction with the chosen academic career. Their study concludes that from different factors social and family factor have the biggest influence on the carrier choice of students. The students feel more confident when they are supported and encouraged by these. Moreover, students feel less satisfaction when they have weak relations with these. Their study suggests that parents should prepare their children for future carrier and must play their role effectively. They should not impose certain goals on children; they should also try to educate themselves about the variety of careers available in post-modern knowledge economy, and not just financially and morally support their children in making the best choices for themselves and the families. Additionally, the government should promote and provide ample opportunities for youth development in all walks of life and not only to professional education in science and technology.

Molnar and Boninger (2020) highlight the problem caused by the commercialization of institutions in America, that focus on money making rather than teaching. Their study highlights the data collection through digital data collecting tools especially during the Covid -19 when online education became common. They illustrated that online companies often market their products to the students, claiming to provide free education to students, this leads to the students' exploitation.

They used a grounded theory approach and identified harmful effect by calling them 'mis-educative'. One of their key findings is that such type of profit gaining undermines the true spirit of learning as school may prioritize financial gaining over the true spirit of education and learning. Their study suggest that schools should focus on the creative learning and to supporting genuine learning of students rather than financial interests. Fernandez, Valsalachandran, and Durgalekshmi (2023) examine the elements that influence the career choices of Indian university students. Their study consists of 375 higher education institutions. Their results show that all factors such as education and family pressure examined weak, correlation with career choice. Similarly, parental pressure has negative effect on the career decisions of students. Support from family members found to have a significant positive impact on career choice of students. Their study suggest that families and institutions can do more to support students in informed decisions by providing guidance and proper information about the new career and opportunities.

Data Analysis

The data analysis in this study explains the imposed career goals resulting from family and institution to the students in the private schools of Tank and Dera Ismail Khan, Pakistan. This paper applies the concept of the Banking Concept of Education developed by Paulo Freire and the Erik Erikson's theory of psychosocial development to determine how the student's decisions are shaped by external pressures originating either from parents or educational institutions. Specifically, this analysis is organized around three major themes: The Negative Implications of Parental Pressure on Career Path, Institutional Agents and the Banking Concept, and Psychological and Physical Effects on Students. All of these reveals different aspect of the imposed goals phenomenon and explain the processes that form student's educational and career background.

Parental Pressure on Career Choice

This first theme has more to do with the influence that parents ought to have when shaping where their children ought to be in the future in

accordance with the Erikson’s psychosocial development theory, specifically the stage of ‘Identity vs. Role Confusion.’. It shows that parents force their children to choose certain fields, such as medicine or engineers regardless of the child’s comfort and desires. The results generated by data analysis indicate a strong relationship. It is possible to staking a high level of relation between family impressions about the choice of a career path, financial expectations, and the level of decision-making freedom regarding these questions among students. That parental decision not only hampers students from choosing career of their interest or dream, but also leading to dissatisfaction, career incompatibility and regret. Results highlight that how influential parental expectations can be in determining the academic and career paths of students, which leads towards stress.

Institutional Influence and the Banking Concept

The second theme investigates how schools act as an agent of imposed goals, with a financial motivation rather than an educative one. Relating to Freire's “Banking Concept of Education”, this theme looks at how schools and teachers urge students for certain career pathways, not to fulfill the educational needs of the learners but to satisfy their own financial interests and gains. The institutions promote affiliated colleges, specific test preparation academies, and career directions

like medicine and engineering in order to increase their profit and business. Thus, they manipulate the students. It is clearly seen that the institutional pressures such as promotion to attend affiliated colleges, bring a stronger connection to students’ autonomy and alignment with interests. This theme reveals how institutional practices reinforce the already existent parental pressures on students while strengthening such pressures through economic benefits, thereby making the choices of students, already weakened, even more limited.

Psychological and Physical Impact on Students

The last theme is the impact of psychological well-being and career satisfaction on students from imposed goals. As the pressures from the family and institutional both combined result in a massive stress and emotional strain on students, leading to career dissatisfaction in many instances. A correlation of regret, desire to change occupations, and perceived lack of career alignment with personal interests underlines the psychological burdens linked to the choice of a career path not in line with one's goals or identity. Students who are pressured by parents and institutions more often feel regretful and wish they could change their chosen career paths. This theme describes how set career aspirations impose a cost on the mind and emotions and become a source of dissatisfaction and pain due to limited self-determination in educational and career choices.

Theme Based Sections

Frequency Analysis of Parental Pressure Variables

	Strongly Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)
Family Opinions on Career	38.03	46.48	11.27	4.23	0.00
Family Pushing Unwanted Career	0.00	52.11	8.45	25.35	14.08
Financial Expectations Influencing Career	22.54	32.39	14.08	19.72	9.86
Freedom in Career Choice	35.21	40.85	0.00	22.54	0.00

	Yes (%)	No (%)
Parents Disregard Career Opinion	22.54	76.06

Family Opinions about Career:

The overall responses, 38.03% strongly agree and 46.48% agree-indicate that choice of career is

seriously influenced by the family's opinion, which again shows strong parental control.

Family Forcing Undesirable Career:

More than half of the respondents agreed that unwanted careers are pushed onto students by families, while 25.35% reflected a disagreeing view of the same issue.

Financial Expectations Influencing Career:

A total of 22.54% strongly agree and 32.39% agree that financial expectations play a significant role in their career decisions, although a fair portion, or 19.72% disagree and 9.86% strongly disagree, feel less impacted.

Freedom of choice in careers:

A combined 76.06% perceive freedom in choosing their careers, although as many as 22.54% disagree, showing a minority that feels restricted. 35.21% strongly agree, while 40.85% simply agree.

Parents Disregard Career Opinion:

From the data, 76.06% agreed that parents respect their career opinions, but the rest 22.54% felt disregarded, again pointing to explain dissatisfaction in some cases.

This raises the strong power of parental opinions and financial expectations toward career decisions and how most feel they can employ some choices. However, the minority that disagrees or feels disregarded shows a great emotional and decisional battle in many students.

Correlation Matrix for Parental Pressure and Career Dissatisfaction Variables

Variables	Spearman Correlations						
	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	X6	X7
Family Opinions on Career	1.00						
Family Pushing Unwanted Career	-.09	1.00					
Parents Disregard Career Opinion	.02	.09	1.00				
Financial Expectations Influencing Career	-.02	-.17	.33*	1.00			
Freedom in Career Choice	.06	.16	-.09	-.20	1.00		
Chosen Wrong Career Due to Pressure	-.17	.02	.25*	.14	-.15	1.00	
Would Change Career if Possible	-.14	.12	.37**	.31*	-.13	.60**	1.00

Note: *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01

Correlation Analysis

Parental influence on career misalignment:

It is positively correlated with Family Pushing Unwanted Career and Chosen Wrong Career Due to Pressure, with $r = .25$, $p < .05$, indicating that family pressure contributes to the misalignment of students with their career choices.

Parental Disregard and Desire for Change of Career

The Parents Disregard Career Opinion correlates positively with Would Change Career, if Possible, $r = .37$, $p < .01$; that is, the less the parental support, the more the students report desire for change of career.

Financial Expectations and Career Dissatisfaction:

The relational effect of Financial Expectations Influencing Career with Would Change Career, if Possible, $r = .31$, $p < .05$, evidences financial stress in career dissatisfaction.

Career Regret and Desire for Change:

This positive correlation with Chosen Wrong Career Due to Pressure and Would Change Career if Possible ($r = .60$, $p < .01$) indicates that students who feel pressured into choosing a career are highly likely also to desire a change.

These correlations indicate that parental pressure, lack of autonomy, and financial expectations are major contributing factors to career dissatisfaction and the desire for career realignment among

students. Again, it connects with the "Banking Concept" of education, where external imposition leads to psychological and career misalignment issues.

Correlation Matrix for Institutional Pressure Variables

Variables	Spearman Correlations					
	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	X6
School Expects Specific Career Path	1.00					
School Encourages Affiliated Colleges	.35	1.00				
School Subtly Encourages Specific Field	.26	.36	1.00			
School Financial Benefits	-.02	.15	.40*	1.00		
Teachers Encourage Personal Academies	.21	.32	.25	.32	1.00	
Teachers Pointed Specific Career	.14	.22	.15	.10	.08	1.00

Note: Correlations > 0.30 are highlighted as moderate.

Moderate Positive Relationships:

School Affiliated colleges and School Subtly Encourages Specific Field remains low at a positive 0.36, which shows that schools subtly encourage their students toward certain fields through their affiliated colleges.

School Subtly Encourages Specific Field and School Financial Benefits are moderately correlated, $r = 0.40$, $p < .05$, suggesting that financial motives may underpin institutional recommendations.

Institutional Coordination:

Teachers Encourage Personal Academies and School Encourages Affiliated Colleges correlate, at best, moderately positive, with $r = 0.32$, to show the possible coherence of teacher recommendations with those of institutional linkages.

Weaker Relationships:

The correlations that involve Teachers Pointed Specific Career and the other variables are rather weaker, $r = 0.15-0.22$, indicating that teacher influence is less important than broader institutional pressures.

Interpretation of Institutional Pressures:

The moderate correlations among variables such as School Expects Specific Career Path, School Financial Benefits, and Teachers Encourage Personal Academies reflect institutional practices that align with the "Banking Concept" of education. This framework suggests that students are directed in ways that serve institutional financial interests rather than their personal goals, reinforcing external control over student autonomy.

Visualization Summary:

The following heatmap displays the dynamics of institutional pressure through highlighting the presence of moderate positive correlations across key variables:

School Helps Affiliated Colleges and School Subtly Encourages Field, $r = 0.36$, suggests schools subtly influence the fields of study by students through affiliated institutions.

School Subtly Encourages Specific Field and School Financial Benefits ($r = 0.40, p < .05$) bring in focus the possible mechanisms of financial incentives in the institutional career recommendations.

The value of $r = 0.32$ indicates a moderate correlation between Teachers Encourage Personal

Academies and School Encourages Affiliated Colleges, which indicates that there is alignment between the teachers' recommendations about Academy membership and those about institutional affiliations. Weaker correlations involving Teachers Pointed Specific Career-or respectively, $r = 0.15-0.22$ -suggest that teacher influence is of limited importance compared to broader institutional pressures.

These findings once again tally well with the "Banking Concept" of education by Freire, where institutional practices in educational institutions rested on organizational interests rather than student autonomy, at best shaping career choice in ways which serve the institutional purpose rather than fostering individual aspiration.

Correlation Matrix for Psychological and Physical Impact Variables

Variables	Spearman Correlations							
	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	X6	X7	X8
Career Choice Aligned with Interest	1.00							
Chosen Wrong Career Due to Pressure	-.36	1.00						
Regret Career Choice	-.43	.58	1.00					
Would Change Career if Possible	-.46	.60**	.96**	1.00				
Freedom in Career Choice	.23	-.15	-.10	-.14	1.00			
Family Opinions on Career	.31	-.19	-.10	-.15	.02	1.00		
Family Pushing Unwanted Career	-.19	.02	.34	.40	.15	-.10	1.00	
Parents Disregard Career Opinion	-.20	.08	.16	.17	-.04	-.23	.35	1.00

Note: * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$

Career Misalignment and Regret:

Career Choice Aligned with Interest shows a negative correlation with Chosen Wrong Career Due to Pressure (-.36), Regret Career Choice (-.43), and Would Change Career if Possible (-.46). This suggests that when students' career choices align with their interests, they have less feelings of regret and are less likely to wish to change their career.

Career Pressure and Dissatisfaction:

Chosen Wrong Career Due to Pressure is positively correlated with Regret Career Choice (.58) and Would Change Career if Possible (.60**). This shows that students who feel that they chose the wrong career due to external pressure, they have feelings of regret and wants to change their careers.

Freedom in Career Choice:

Freedom in Career Choice shows weak correlations with other variables, which is suggesting that perceived freedom may not have a strong direct relationship with career dissatisfaction.

Parental Influence:

Family Opinions on Career and Family Pushing Unwanted Career show slight correlations with dissatisfaction variables, but none of them are notably strong. This could imply that while family opinions affect career decisions, and their direct impact on dissatisfaction is less pronounced compared to other pressures.

Visualization Summary:

Parental Disregard and Career Regret:

Parents Disregard Career Opinion has weak positive correlations with Regret Career Choice (.16) and Would Change Career, if Possible (.17), hinting that disregard for students' career preferences might slightly influence regret and a desire for change.

High Positive Correlations:

Would Change Career, if Possible, strongly correlates with Regret Career Choice (0.96) and Chosen Wrong Career Due to Pressure (0.60), highlighting the connection between external pressure, career dissatisfaction, and regret.

Regret Career Choice positively correlates with Chosen Wrong Career Due to Pressure (0.58), emphasizing regret as a common outcome of misaligned career paths.

Career Interest and Pressure:

Career Choice Aligned with Interest negatively correlates with Would Change Career, if Possible (-0.46), Regret Career Choice (-0.43), and Chosen Wrong Career Due to Pressure (-0.36). This underscores that alignment with personal interests reduces dissatisfaction and regret.

Parental and Institutional Influence:

Mild positive correlations for Family Opinions on Career (0.31) and Freedom in Career Choice (0.23) with satisfaction indicators suggest that supportive environments can mitigate negative effects of external pressures.

Psychological and Physical Impact

Using the heatmap, some of the important relationships among career satisfaction, regret, and pressures from other quarters are: the negative relationship between Career Choice Aligned with Interest and Chosen Wrong Career Due to Pressure is -0.36, Regret Career Choice at -0.43, while Would Change Career, if Possible, at -0.46. This points out that interest-based career decisions reduce dissatisfaction and regret.

While, Chosen Wrong Career Due to Pressure is highly related conceptually to Regret Career Choice (0.58) and to Would Change Career, if Possible (0.60**), in so doing underlining the negative impact of pressures from outside on the satisfaction with one's career, the weak correlations of Freedom in Career Choice and parental influence would hint at a limited direct effect compared to broader pressures.

Overall, career choices must coincide with personal interests, and the impact of external influences in these choices must be minimized in order to lessen dissatisfaction and to develop a career that is gratifying.

So, in the light of Erik Erikson's Psychosocial Development Theory stage five and Paulo Freire's "Banking Concept of Education", this data reflects the selfish nature of institutions and teachers in the schools. Teachers' role as the decider of the carrier of students for the material gain raises a question about their true role as a true teacher. Similarly,

parents molding their children goals shows cruelty towards students instead of loving and caring. Students feel confused about their role, regret and are dissatisfied about their future.

Moreover, teachers and institutions commit a heinous act by filling the innocent minds of students with certain career and keeping them to a certain track for their own material gains. This creates a situation of psychological sufferings for students who are unable to achieve their imposed goals in the long run. As a result, students become socially alienated and want to change their career. Additionally, they are overwhelmed by a variety of thoughts even suicidal thoughts because they are unable to hunt their imposed dream.

Furthermore, parents' strict role in determining the academic success of students undermines their career. Parents create hurdles on the road to success, tying students to the ropes of imposed goals.

Conclusion

The overall discussion reveals that the parents and institutions play a significant role in imposing goals on students. Parents, who should support their children in choosing their own field of interest, instead impose their own goals on them. Similarly, the very institutions that work as the ambassadors of education become source of material gain. They willingly direct students'

attention to certain fields that benefit educational business tycoons. Parents and teachers create a web of imposed goals around students that mentally torture them in the long run. Parents and institutions are the supreme authorities and students are marionette in their hands. They place them where they want without the students' free will. They change the overall position and shift of students. Their wrong decisions create very serious problems for the students who never wanted to choose the specific goals created for them. This creates the psychological problems for students who wish to change their career but are unable to change it.

In Pakistan, particularly in District Tank and District Dera Ismail Khan, the psychological suffering of oppressed and the marginalized students can be minimized if parents and teachers should not impose certain goals or careers on the students. They should allow the students to choose their own carrier freely without the institutional and parental pressure. Parents should help students in highlighting the pros and cons of certain careers to students but they should not instruct them to go for any specific career. Teachers and Institutions should act as facilitators, quenching students' thirst for knowledge. They should instill a sense of freedom in the students. They should not make students as a commodity for the material gains in the class room. They should teach them how to live a life full of freedom rather than making their life burdensome. They should remain neutral in students' career choices and strive to avoid exploiting them.

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